

Gesture-to-Text Translator Using Arduino and Android Application

Senior Project

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to my esteemed doctor Mohamad Baydoun, whose wisdom, encouragement, and guidance have been a constant source of inspiration throughout this journey.

To my beloved family and friends, thank you for your endless love, patience, and support.

Your faith in me has given me the strength to persevere and succeed.

And most importantly, to every deaf-mute person around the world, this project is for you.

May it help to break barriers and bring people closer through the power of understanding and communication.

Mohammed S. Zreik

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This is only the beginning, and with your support, I'm inspired to keep reaching higher and creating more.

“The more you know, the more you realise how much you don't know

The less you know, the more you think you know.”

Hussein A. Moussa

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ABSTRACT

This project presents the design and development of a Gesture-to-Text Translator System to improve communication for individuals with hearing or speech impairments. The system uses a wearable glove equipped with flex sensors to detect hand gestures, which are processed by an Arduino microcontroller and transmitted wirelessly to an Android application via an HC-05 Bluetooth module. The mobile application displays the translated text in real-time. Through careful calibration and user interface optimization, the system minimizes latency and ensures accurate gesture recognition. The solution is portable, cost-effective, and adaptable, making it suitable for everyday use. This work not only demonstrates the feasibility of the gesture-to-text translation using low-cost components but also lays the groundwork for future work such as voice output, expanded gesture libraries, and machine learning-based classification. The system contributes towards more inclusive communication technologies and offers potential for further research and development in assistive devices.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

ADC: Analog-to-Digital Converter

AI: Artificial Intelligence

APK: Android Package Kit

API: Application Programming Interface

ASL: American Sign Language

CNN: Convolutional Neural Network

GCP: Google Cloud Platform

ICSP: In-Circuit Serial Programming

IDE: Integrated Development Environment

IEEE: Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

ISO: International Organization for Standardization

k Ω : Kilo-ohm

LDP: Lebanese Deaf Population

ML: Machine Learning

PWM: Pulse Width Modulation

SPP: Serial Port Profile

WHO: World Health Organization

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Deaf people are individuals who experience varying degrees of hearing loss, which can range from partial to complete deafness.

Deafness may be present from birth or acquired later in life due to illness, injury, or aging. While some deaf individuals may use hearing aids, others rely on sign language as their primary mode of communication [1].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 5% of the world population suffers from hearing loss. In percentage, this number may seem lower, but when it comes to numbers, more than 430 million people in the World are deaf or have hearing loss problems [2].

Estimates of the deaf population in Lebanon vary, with figures ranging from 12,000 to 26,000 individuals. The International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology reports approximately 26,000 deaf individuals in Lebanon, representing about 0.5% of the country's population [1].

Shown in **Figure 1-1: LDP distribution by governorates** is the Lebanese deaf population (LDP) location distribution by governorates:

LDP Location Distribution by Governorates

Figure 1-1: LDP distribution by governorates

The global prevalence of hearing loss has been steadily increasing over the years. One of the most common causes of this upward trend is not genetic factors as many people would think, but in fact, it's loud noise exposure such as gunshots, firecrackers and explosions, particularly prolonged exposure either in the workplace or recreationally, can damage the delicate mechanisms inside the ear. If you are standing next to someone, yet have to shout to be heard, you can be sure that the noise is loud enough to damage your ears [3].

There are many other factors, as shown in **Figure 2-1: Causes of Hearing Loss**.

Figure 2-1: Causes of Hearing Loss

By 2050, nearly 2.5 billion people are expected to have some degree of hearing loss, and at least 700 million will require rehabilitation [4], as shown in the below:

Figure 3-1: Projected number of people with hearing loss

1.2 Problem Statement

Sign language is a method of communication through gestures, facial expressions, and body language, particularly through the use of hands and arms when spoken communication is impossible or not desirable.

Various sign languages are used around the world. Like spoken language, sign languages developed naturally through different groups of people interacting with each other, so there are many varieties. There are somewhere between 138 and 300 different types of sign language used around the globe today. Interestingly, most countries that share the same spoken language do not necessarily have the same sign language. English, for example, has three varieties: American Sign Language, British Sign Language, and Australian Sign Language [5].

In addition, we face a predominant reliance on spoken language in most societies. This problem is further increased by the limited knowledge about sign language as a primary means of communication and the challenges in accessing appropriate communication support services. As a result, this communication mode is said to be complex for a normal person to understand. Thus, deaf-mute people face several difficulties throughout their lives, from childhood, during their educational journey, until adulthood, during their work process [1].

1.3 General overview of the project

This project aims to bridge the gap between the deaf-mute community and the general population by converting gestures into text. Through this system, individuals who rely on sign language will be able to express their emotions, share their opinions, and engage more seamlessly in social interactions without feeling distanced or isolated.

Additionally, this project has potential applications in education, healthcare, and career opportunities for people with hearing and speech disabilities.

Communication is the act of conveying and exchanging information, which can only be effective when all participants share a common language. However, sign language is not universally understood, creating challenges for those who rely on it. To address this issue, this project proposes a glove-based system that translates hand gestures into text, facilitating communication for deaf-mute individuals in their daily lives.

The system utilizes five flex sensors, one on each finger, to measure the degree of bending in real time. These sensor readings are processed to recognize specific hand gestures corresponding to predefined words. The recognized gestures are translated into text, which is then transmitted using a Bluetooth module and displayed on an Android device, allowing for real-time communication. Gesture processing is achieved using an Arduino microcontroller, ensuring an efficient and portable solution.

Previous translation systems have faced challenges such as bulky designs or limited functionality, for example, only translating individual letters, making communication slow and inefficient [6].

This project aims to overcome these limitations by providing a compact, real-time, and user-friendly solution. By leveraging sensor technology and microcontroller processing, this system offers an innovative approach to enhancing communication accessibility for the deaf-mute community.

1.4 Thesis Outline

This report is structured into five chapters, each providing essential information about the project.

- **Chapter 1** presents statistical data on the deaf-mute community, explains the fundamentals of sign language, discusses the challenges faced by individuals with hearing and speech impairments, and outlines the objectives of this project.
- **Chapter 2** reviews similar sign language translation projects, compares them, mentioning their advantages and disadvantages, and demonstrates what we learned from them and our motivation.
- **Chapter 3** details the system design, including hardware requirements and use case diagrams, to illustrate the technical and non-technical aspects supporting the system's functionality.
- **Chapter 4** describes the key implementation and simulation tools used and the test cases employed to evaluate system performance.
- **Chapter 5** summarizes the lessons learned from this project and suggests potential improvements to enhance its effectiveness.

CHAPTER 2

SURVEY OF EXISTING METHODS AND SIMILAR SYSTEMS

2.1 Introduction

Traditional methods of communication between the deaf and normal people, such as writing or text-based communication, can be slow and inconvenient, especially in social life. In the development of a glove-based translator system, it's essential to review existing methods and similar systems to identify advancements, limitations, and potential areas for improvement. Various approaches have been explored in prior research, including sensor-based gloves with machine learning (ML) algorithm, a generative Artificial intelligence powered (AI) sign language translator that uses (AI) to convert speech or text into animated American Sign Language (ASL), and a Sign Language Interpreter using Deep Learning.

2.2 System 1: Sign language glove using Machine Learning (ML)

Monica Lin and Roberto Villalba designed and built a glove to be worn on the right hand that uses (ML) to translate sign language into spoken English [7]. Every person's hand is a unique size and shape, so they aimed to create a device that could provide reliable translations regardless of those differences. The device uses five Flex-Sensors that are used to quantify how much each finger is bent, and the MPU-6050 (a three-axis accelerometer and gyroscope) can detect the orientation and rotational movement of the hand. These sensors are read, averaged, and arranged into packets using an ATmega1284p microcontroller. These packets are then sent serially to a user's PC to be run in conjunction with a Python script. The user creates data sets of information from the glove for each gesture that should eventually be translated, and the algorithm trains over these datasets to predict later at runtime what a user is signing, as shown

in **Figure 4-2: ASL signs for “A”, “B”, and “C”** and **Figure 5-2: Implementation of ASL signs on the glove**.

Figure 4-2: ASL signs for “A”, “B”, and “C”

Figure 5-2: Implementation of ASL signs on the glove

2.3 System 2: GenAI

GenAI-powered Global Sign Language Translator [8] is an innovative solution that uses generative (AI) to convert speech or text into animated American Sign Language (ASL). By efficiently generating ASL animations, it breaks the limitations of traditional tools and enhances social inclusivity, providing valuable support for the hearing-impaired community. This project is developed using the GCP Platform, translation API, and Vertex AI.

Figure 6-2: GenAI Graphical Interface

2.4 System 3: Sign Language Interpreter using Deep Learning

The sign language interpreter using deep learning [9] uses video feed from the camera to recognize the sign language in real time and provide the sign interpretations immediately. They used a custom data set of various (ASL) with deep learning (CNN) to train a model to recognize the signs in real time, and Python to implement deep learning thus achieving a 96% accuracy.

Figure 7-2: Implementation demo

2.5 Systems Comparison

- **System 1 - Advantages:**

1. **Real-Time Translation** – Uses (ML) to efficiently translate sign language.
2. **Machine Learning Flexibility** – The model can be trained to recognize custom gestures, making it useful beyond standard sign language translation.
3. **High Sensor Accuracy** - Five flex sensors and an accelerometer/gyroscope ensure precise finger bending and hand movement detection.

- **Shortcomings:**

1. **Wired Connection** – The glove transmits data to a PC, which limits mobility.
2. **Limited to Right-Hand Use** – Designed specifically for the right hand, which may not be suitable for left-handed individuals or users with mobility impairments.
3. **Potential Sensor Limitations** – Flex sensors can degrade over time, leading to accuracy issues.

- **System 2 - Advantages:**

1. **Bridges Communication Gaps** – Converts speech or text into ASL animations.
2. **Generative AI for Realistic Animations** - This tool uses AI to generate lifelike ASL animations rather than relying on pre-recorded clips, making it more flexible.
3. **Support for Multiple Input Modes** – Can process both spoken and written language.

- **Shortcomings:**

1. **Limited to ASL** – Currently supports only (ASL), limiting its use.
2. **Dependence on Cloud Services** – Requires internet access.
3. **Potential Latency Issues** – Real-time ASL generation depends on processing speed, which could cause slight delays in communication.

- **System 3 - Advantages:**

1. **High Accuracy** – The deep learning model provides reliable sign language recognition.
2. **Real-Time Processing** – Uses a live video feed to interpret signs immediately, making it fast and practical for real-world use.
3. **No Wearable Hardware Needed** – Unlike glove-based solutions, this approach does not require users to wear additional devices, making it more accessible.

- **Shortcomings:**

1. **Requires a Camera and Good Lighting** – Performance may degrade in low-light conditions or with poor camera quality.
2. **Fixed to ASL** – The system may not work for other sign languages without retraining on additional datasets.
3. **Potential Processing Delays** – Real-time deep learning models can be computationally intensive, requiring powerful hardware for smooth performance.

Table 1-2: Comparison Table Based on Accuracy & Performance

Criterion 1	System 1	System 2	System 3
Accuracy & Performance			
High Accuracy	✓	✗	✓
Real-Time Processing	✓	✓	✓
Requires Large Dataset	✗	✓	✓
Noise Resistance	✓	✓	✗

Table 2-2: Comparison Table Based on Hardware & Implementation

Criterion 2	System 1	System 2	System 3
Hardware & Implementation			
Requires Special Hardware	✓	✗	✓
Portable	✗	✓	✗
Low Power Consumption	✓	✗	✗
Easy to Set Up	✗	✓	✗

Table 3-2: Comparison Table Based on Usability & Accessibility

Criterion 3	System 1	System 2	System 3
Usability & Accessibility			
User Training Required	✓	✗	✗
Supports Different Hand Sizes	✗	✓	✓
Works for Any Sign Language	✗	✗	✓
Scalable	✗	✓	✓

2.6 Conclusion and Motivation

Existing methods for sign language translation, including video-based deep learning models, AI-powered animation tools, and sensor-equipped gloves, each offer unique advantages but also have notable limitations. Video-based systems provide high accuracy but require extensive datasets and computational resources. AI-driven sign language animation tools improve accessibility but may struggle with precise hand movements. Sensor-based gloves offer real-time gesture recognition but are often limited by wired connections, hand-size variations, and the need for extensive user training.

Our motivation comes from the need for a more portable, user-friendly, and adaptable sign language translation system. The proposed methodology aims for high accuracy, real-time responsiveness, and broader accessibility while addressing key limitations in current solutions.

While our project demonstrates a highly accurate Gesture-to-Text translation system, future work will focus on optimizing usability, improving sensor reliability, and exploring new applications beyond sign language, such as gesture-based command interfaces for assistive technologies, gaming, and human-computer interaction.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM DESIGN

3.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the key components of the system design, including its requirements, architecture, and various modeling diagrams, such as use case, sequence, and class diagrams, to illustrate the overall structure and functionality. By defining these elements, we aim to establish a well-organized approach that guides the development process effectively.

3.2 Requirements and Specification Analysis

This section provides a clear understanding of the requirements and specifications that form the foundation of our project. It covers various aspects, such as functional requirements, including use case diagrams, system architecture, class diagrams, and other essential components. This section will also address non-functional elements, including financial viability, stakeholders, risks, ethical considerations, and sustainability.

The primary objective of this section is to ensure that all requirements and specifications are well-documented and analyzed in detail.

3.2.1 Functional Requirements

The functional requirements of this project define the core operations and activities that the system must be able to perform. These requirements ensure that the translation system is efficient, accurate, and user-friendly. Below is a list of key functional requirements:

- **Real-time processing of gestures** - The system should recognize and display sign interpretations within 3 seconds.
- **Accurate translation of gestures** - The glove must accurately detect and classify hand gestures.
- **Customization & Adaptability** - The system must enable users to customize gestures to improve recognition based on their signing style.
- **Hardware durability** - The glove should remain functional, reliable, and comfortable over time, even with frequent use in various environments.
- **Future Expansion** - The design should allow for future upgrades, including additional languages.
- **Portable Use** - The design should allow the glove to be used in various settings (e.g., home, school, work).

3.2.2 Use Case Diagrams

A use case diagram is a visual representation of the interactions between a system and its users (actors). It helps define the system's functional requirements by illustrating how users interact with it to achieve specific goals. We will be demonstrating use case diagrams for the following actors: Deaf, Normal Person, and System. We will also show the actions that every one of those actors can perform.

Figure 8-3: Use Case Diagram

The above use case diagram is used to understand how the system works and how the users interact with it. It includes the following:

❖ **The Deaf** as the primary actor who can do the following actions:

- Wear the glove and ensure it fits properly.
- Calibrates the flex sensors to ensure accurate gesture recognition.
- Performs a gesture using their hand.
- Correct any misinterpreted gestures by recalibrating or repeating the gesture.

❖ **The System** as the secondary actor, which can do the following actions:

- Captures finger bending data and sends it to the Arduino Uno.
- Processes the sensor data to identify the gesture.
- Translates the recognized gesture into text.
- Displays the translated text on an Android device.

❖ **The normal person** also acts as a secondary actor who reads the text displayed on the smartphone.

3.3 System Architecture

The system architecture is the “blueprint” of the system, which includes the fundamental technologies used as well as the dataflow. The system architecture can also be defined using a layered architecture approach, which organizes the system into distinct layers, each responsible for specific tasks.

The System can be divided into the following layers:

1. **Input Layer:** Forms the system's foundation, where physical components like flex sensors and the microcontroller work together to capture hand gestures. Flex sensors measure finger bending as the user performs gestures. These sensors generate analog signals proportional to the degree of bending, which the microcontroller then reads. It acts as the interface between the physical world and the digital system, ensuring that the data from the sensors is accurately captured and prepared for further processing.
2. **Processing Layer:** Responsible for transforming the raw analog signals from the flex sensors into meaningful digital data. The microcontroller plays a central role here, as it processes the incoming signals to filter out noise and normalize the data. By converting the analog signals into a digital format, the system is able to interpret the gestures accurately.
3. **Feature Extraction Layer:** focuses on extracting specific attributes, such as finger bending angles, which are essential for distinguishing between different gestures.
4. **Gesture Recognition Layer:** matches the extracted features to a predefined set of gestures. Once a match is found, the system identifies the corresponding gesture, enabling it to proceed to the final stage of the process.
5. **Output Layer:** delivers the results of the gesture recognition process to the user.

System Architecture for Gesture-to-Text Translator Glove

Figure 9-3: System Architecture

3.4 Class Diagrams

A class diagram captures the system's static design view, including the classes, their attributes, methods, and relationships. The system focuses on three components:

Flex Sensors, Arduino Uno, and a Smartphone. To make the diagram more complete, we can define the relationships between the classes and include multiplicity where applicable.

Multiplicity specifies how many instances of one class are associated with another class.

Table 4-3: Class Diagram Symbols

Symbol	Meaning
1	One and only one
*	From 0 to
Dashed arrow	Dependency
Filled diamond	Composition

Figure 10-3: Class Diagram

3.5 Sequence Diagrams

The Sequence Diagram illustrates the step-by-step interactions between different components of the translation system in a time-ordered manner.

As shown in **Figure 11-3: Sequence Diagram**.

Figure 11-3: Sequence Diagram

Here is a detailed breakdown of how the system functions:

1. **User Performs a Gesture:** The user moves their fingers to form a specific sign.
2. **Flex Sensors Capture Data:** The flex sensors measure the bending of each finger.
3. **Arduino Reads Sensor Data:** The Arduino collects data from all sensors.
4. **Arduino Compares Data with Stored Gestures:** The system checks if the captured gesture matches any predefined gestures stored in memory. If a match is found, the corresponding text for the gesture is retrieved; if not, the display stays empty.
5. **Data is sent to Bluetooth module:** The mapped text corresponding to the recognized gesture is sent to the Bluetooth module for transmission.
6. **Data transmission to Smartphone:** The translated text is transmitted to a Smartphone.

7. **Smartphone Displays Translated Text:** The Smartphone screen shows the recognized gesture in text format.
8. **User Reads Display Output:** The user views the translated text.
9. **System Awaits New Gesture:** The process resets, allowing the user to perform another gesture.

3.6 Activity Diagrams

The Activity Diagram represents the sequence of actions in the translation system, from capturing a gesture to displaying the corresponding text on a Smartphone screen, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 12-3: Activity Diagram

Here is a step-by-step description of the process:

1. **Start:** The system begins when the user performs a hand gesture.
2. **Perform Gesture:** The user moves their fingers to form a specific sign.
3. **Capture Sensor Data:** The flex sensors on the glove detect finger bending.
4. **Process Sensor Data:** The Arduino collects and processes data from the sensors.
5. **Compare with Stored Gestures:** The system checks if the captured gesture matches a predefined gesture in its database.
6. **Decision Step:**
 - **If a match is found:** The corresponding text is retrieved from memory.
 - **If no match is found:** The display is empty.
7. **Send Output to Bluetooth Module:** The output data is sent to the Bluetooth module for transmission.
8. **Transmit data to a Smartphone:** The output data is transmitted to a Smartphone.
9. **Display on Smartphone screen:** The translated text is displayed on the screen for the user to read.
10. **User Reads Display:** The user sees the translated text, completing the interaction.
11. **End:** The process concludes, and the system waits for the next gesture.

3.7 Entity-Relationship (ER) Diagrams

Since our project does not involve the use of a database or any structured data storage system, an Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram is not applicable.

3.8 Non-Technical Aspects

3.8.1 Financial Viability

A cost-benefit analysis helps to evaluate the project by comparing the estimated costs with the potential benefits. The table below outlines the costs and expected benefits.

Table 5-3: Estimated Costs

Hardware Used	Estimated Cost (USD)
Arduino Board	7 \$
Flex Sensors (5x)	60 \$
Bluetooth Module	6 \$
Power Supply (Battery)	4 \$
Wires & Connectors	1 \$
Resistors (5x)	5 \$
Glove	1 \$
Total	84 \$

Expected Benefits:

-**Accessibility:** Helps individuals with hearing impairments communicate effectively. -

Affordability: Lower-cost alternative to expensive commercial translation systems.

-**Portability:** Compact and wearable, making it practical for daily use.

Table 6-3: Cost vs. Benefit Evaluation

Factor	Cost Impact	Benefit
Development & Materials	Medium	Long-term usability
Market Potential	Medium	High (Potential for commercial use)
Maintenance & Upgrades	Low	Customizable & expandable

3.8.2 Stakeholders

This project primarily benefits deaf-mute individuals. It enables them to communicate more effectively by translating gestures into text, enhancing their daily interactions. Caregivers and family members also benefit from this project, as it improves the overall quality of interactions. Additionally, businesses and customer service centers can integrate this technology to create a more inclusive environment for their employees and customers with hearing impairments.

Despite these benefits, some groups may be negatively impacted by this technology. For instance, traditional sign language interpreters might experience reduced demand for their services. Additionally, companies developing similar systems could face market competition, especially if this system offers a more cost-effective and user-friendly alternative.

Several key stakeholders should have a say in how this project is developed and implemented. The deaf-mute communities, sign language experts, engineers, and developers are crucial contributors, as their feedback ensures that the device works accurately and effectively.

3.8.3 Scope

This project focuses on developing a glove-based system that translates hand gestures into text displayed on an Android device. The glove will use flex sensors to detect finger bending, an Arduino microcontroller to process the sensor data, and a Bluetooth module to transmit the data to an Android device. The system is designed to support a predefined set of custom gestures programmed by the user.

The project will not include voice output or translation to multiple sign languages. It will not integrate machine learning for adaptive recognition. The primary focus is on portable, real-time, gesture-to-text conversion to provide an accessible and affordable communication aid.

3.8.4 Risks

Several factors could impact the successful implementation of this glove-based gesture translation system:

1. **Hardware Limitations** – The accuracy of gesture recognition depends on the quality and sensitivity of the flex sensors. Malfunctions could reduce reliability.
2. **Power Consumption** – The system is battery-operated; frequent recharging or battery replacement may be required, affecting usability.
3. **User Adaptability** – Users may need time to learn how to use the glove correctly.
4. **Wear and Tear** – Continuous use may cause physical wear on the glove and sensors, potentially requiring regular maintenance or replacement.

3.8.5 Schedule and Milestones

Table 7-3: Scheduling Tasks and Milestones

Task Name	Start Date	Finish Date	Duration	Weeks
Project idea selection and approval	Feb 17	Feb 19	3 days	1
Researching and writing chapter 1	Fed 20	Fed 25	6 days	1-2
Researching and writing chapter 2	Feb 26	Mar 9	12 days	2-4
Researching and writing chapter 3	Mar 10	Mar 23	14 days	4-6
Hardware component selection	Mar 24	Apr 6	14 days	6-8
Building hardware and demonstration	Apr 7	Apr 20	14 days	8-10
Android app development	Apr 21	Apr 27	7 days	10-11
Writing chapter 4	Apr 28	May 4	7 days	11-12
Writing chapter 5 and finalizing the report	May 5	May 11	7 days	12-13
Testing and final changes	May 12	May 29	18 days	13-15

3.8.6 Ethical and Social Considerations

There are several ethical considerations to keep in mind when designing a glove-based translator system. These issues are important to ensure the project is inclusive, respectful, and beneficial to the deaf community. Here are some ethical concerns:

- ❖ **Accessibility and Affordability:** The design should be affordable and user-friendly, ensuring accessibility for all, regardless of financial or technical background.
- ❖ **Accuracy and Reliability:** Inaccurate translations could lead to harm in critical situations. To ensure reliability in high-stakes scenarios, clearly address the limitations of the system to users and provide guidance on when and how it should be used.

3.8.7 Environmental and Sustainability Considerations

This project has a minimal environmental impact as it primarily involves low-power electronic components such as flex sensors and an Arduino microcontroller.

3.8.8 Relevant Standards

The technical (and possibly the non-technical) relevant standards to this system are:

- **Sensor Standards - IEEE 1451:** Smart transducers standard to ensure accurate and consistent data acquisition.
- **Accessibility Standards – ISO/IEC 29138:** This is relevant since the project is designed to assist individuals with hearing or speech impairments, aligning with standards for accessible technologies.
- **Bluetooth Communication Standard – IEEE 802.15.1:** This standard governs short-range wireless communication using Bluetooth, which is used to transmit data from the Arduino to the Android device.
- **Software Engineering: Product Quality – ISO/IEC 9126:** Applicable for evaluating the quality attributes of the Android application, including usability, efficiency, and reliability.

3.9 Conclusion

In this chapter, we have comprehensively explored the System Design of the Gesture-to-Text translator glove. The chapter began with an Introduction outlining the system's purpose and scope. Through Requirements and Specification Analysis, we identified the key technical and functional requirements necessary for the system to operate effectively, ensuring it meets the needs of its intended users.

The Functional Requirements and Use Case Diagrams provided a clear understanding of the system's capabilities and interactions, highlighting how users will engage with the system.

The System Architecture laid the foundation for the hardware and software integration, while the Class Diagrams, Sequence Diagrams, and Activity Diagrams detailed the structural and behavioral aspects of the system, ensuring an efficient design.

Beyond the technical aspects, this chapter also addresses Non-Technical considerations, including financial viability, stakeholder analysis, project scope, and risk management. The Schedule and Milestones provided a realistic timeline for development, ensuring the project remains on track.

Ethical and social considerations were thoroughly examined to ensure the system respects Deaf culture, promotes inclusivity, and addresses potential privacy concerns.

Additionally, environmental and sustainability considerations were discussed, concluding that the project has minimal environmental impact due to its small scale and use of low-power components.

Finally, adherence to Relevant Standards ensures the system aligns with industry best practices and regulatory requirements.

CHAPTER 4

IMPLEMENTATION/SIMULATION AND TESTING

4.1 Introduction

To benefit from all the services of the Gesture-to-Text Translator Glove, this project went through several phases of implementation, simulation, and testing. This chapter will showcase the tools used to achieve the system's final functionality, as well as an overview of the implementation itself.

4.2 Implementation Tools

In this section, we will list the required software and hardware tools for the Project.

1- Arduino Uno

Arduino UNO is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P. It has 14 digital input/output pins (6 of which can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button [10]. The board reads analog signals from the flex sensors, processes the data using a predefined algorithm, and generates the corresponding text output.

Figure 13-4: Arduino Uno R3

2- Flex Sensors

Flex sensors are bendable resistive sensors that change their resistance when bent. They're available in various sizes, but the ones we're using are 2.2 inches and 4.5 inches. Although the sizes are different, the basic function remains the same. They are also divided based on resistance. There are LOW resistance, MEDIUM resistance, and HIGH resistance types [11].

Figure 14-4: Flex Sensor

As shown in the figure below, the flex sensor maintains its nominal resistance when it's in a straight position. As the sensor bends, the resistance increases proportionally to the angle. At a 45° bend, the resistance doubles, while at a 90° bend, it can reach up to four times the nominal value. This linear relationship between bending angle and resistance allows the flex sensor to effectively translate angular displacement into a measurable resistance parameter.

Figure 15-4: Flex Sensor Bending Angles

For the microcontroller to read the flex sensor's output, the resistance must be converted to a voltage parameter. This is achieved using a voltage divider circuit [11], as illustrated in the figure below. The voltage divider allows variations in the sensor's resistance to produce proportional voltage changes, which the ADC can then interpret to get the digital value.

Figure 16-4: Voltage Divider Circuit

As shown above, R₁ is a resistor of fixed resistance, V_o is the voltage across the flex sensor, P₁ and P₂ are the terminals of the flex sensor. V_o is calculated using this equation:

$$V_o = VCC (R_x / (R_1 + R_x))$$

3- HC-05 Bluetooth Module

The HC-05 is a popular low-cost, easy-to-use Bluetooth module designed to enable wireless serial communication between microcontrollers and devices like smartphones, tablets, and PCs. It supports 2.4GHz radio transceiver and baseband. It operates over a range of up to 10 meters in open space. Primarily, the HC-05 is used in embedded projects to add wireless control or data transfer features, commonly pairing with Arduino, ESP32, or Raspberry Pi boards. It supports Serial Port Profile (SPP), making it suitable for serial communication.

The module can operate in master or slave mode. By default, it starts in slave mode but can be configured to act as a master using AT commands [12].

Figure 17-4: HC-05 Bluetooth Module

4- Resistors

Resistors are used in conjunction with the flex sensors to create voltage dividers, which help in converting the resistance changes into measurable voltage values. The resistors used in the project are 10 k Ω for each sensor.

5- Arduino IDE

Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment) is an open-source software designed by Arduino and mainly used for writing, compiling, and uploading code to almost all microcontroller Modules.

6- Android Studio IDE

Android Studio is the official IDE for Android app development. It is used to develop the mobile application that receives gesture data from the Arduino (via HC-05 Bluetooth) and displays the translated text on an Android device.

4.3 Implementation Summary

The implementation of the Gesture-to-Text translator glove involves hardware integration, sensor calibration, data processing, and output display. The system captures gestures through flex sensors, processes the sensor readings using an Arduino, and displays the corresponding text output on an Android device. Below is a summary of the implementation process:

1. Hardware Setup

- **Flex Sensors:** Five flex sensors are attached to the glove to detect finger bending.

Figure 18-4: Implementation Glove

- **Resistors:** Five 10 k Ω resistors to create a voltage divider for each sensor.

- **Arduino Board:** Reads sensor data, processes it, and sends the corresponding output.

Figure 19-4: Implementation Board

- **Android App:** Displays the recognized text output corresponding to the gesture.

Figure 20-4: App Implementation Output

2. Sensor Calibration

- Calibration is performed by recording sensor values for known gestures and establishing threshold values as shown in the figure below.

Figure 21-4: Sensor Calibration

3. Data Processing and Gesture Recognition

- The Arduino reads analog values from the flex sensors.
- The collected data is compared against predefined threshold values to determine the performed gesture.

```
// Define individual thresholds for each sensor  
int thresholds[5] = {537, 520, 541, 512, 758}; // Adjust as needed
```

Figure 22-4: Threshold values

4. Displaying Recognized Gestures

- The recognized gestures are converted into predefined text, which is then sent to an Android device, allowing for real-time Gesture-to-Text translation. For example, the table below illustrates some phrases/words and their corresponding gestures.

Table 8-4: Predefined Words & Gestures Dataset

Phrases/Words	Hand Gesture	Phrases/Words	Hand Gesture
Hello!			
How are you?			
Stop			
Thank you			
Good bye!			
Good night			
I am sick			
I am hungry			

5. IDE Code

- The sketch begins by including the software serial library for the Bluetooth module and defining its TX and RX to pins 8 and 7. Then we define the sensor pins from the thumb (A0) to the little finger (A4) as shown below.

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
SoftwareSerial Bluetooth(7, 8); // TX to D7, RX to D8

// Define sensor pins for Thumb to Little finger
int flexSensorPins[5] = {A0, A1, A2, A3, A4};
```

Figure 23-4: Defining Pins

- After that, we set up the condition to read and convert the sensor values to 1 = bent and 0 = unbent as shown in **Figure 24-4: Bent/Unbent Condition**.

```
// Read and convert sensor values into gesture code
for (int i = 0; i < 5; i++) {
  int sensorValue = analogRead(flexSensorPins[i]);
  Serial.print("Sensor ");
  Serial.print(i);
  Serial.print(": ");
  Serial.println(sensorValue);

  if (sensorValue > thresholds[i]) {
    gestureCode += "1"; // Bent
  } else {
    gestureCode += "0"; // Unbent
  }
}
```

Figure 24-4: Bent/Unbent Condition

- Next, match sensor data to the predefined gesture codes and send the output text via Bluetooth. As shown in the figure below, we also add a 1 second delay between words/phrases.

```
// Match gesture to predefined phrases
String message = mapGestureToPhrase(gestureCode);

// Send to Bluetooth
Bluetooth.println(message);
Serial.println("Detected: " + message);

delay(1000);
```

Figure 25-4: Reading Analog Values

- Each gesture is identified by a unique combination of values. The program uses if and else if statements to compare the sensor values with predefined thresholds, which will then be converted to either 1 or 0 (1= bent / 0 = unbent).

If a match is found, the corresponding message is sent to the connected device. For instance, if all fingers are 1 except the thumb, the connected device will display "How are you?" after a delay of 1 second.

However, if no match is found, nothing will be displayed as illustrated in Figure 26-4: **Predefined values/Gesture.**

```
String mapGestureToPhrase(String code) {
  if (code == "10000") return "Hello!";
  else if (code == "01111") return "How are you?";
  else if (code == "11111") return "STOP!";
  else if (code == "00011") return "Thank you";
  else if (code == "10001") return "Good bye!";
  else if (code == "10010") return "Good night";
  else if (code == "00110") return "I am sick";
  else if (code == "11110") return "I am hungry";
  else if (code == "10111") return "I need water";
  else if (code == "10110") return "I feel sleepy";
  else if (code == "00111") return "Good work!";
  else if (code == "01110") return "Sorry";
  else if (code == "11000") return "Exactly!";
  else if (code == "00001") return "Please!";
  else if (code == "10011") return "I am deaf mute";
  else return "";
}
```

Figure 26-4: Predefined values/Gesture

4.4 Test Cases and Acceptance Criteria

To ensure the proper functionality of the project, various test cases were conducted using Tinkercad for simulation. The system was tested for accurate gesture recognition and sensor responsiveness, as shown below:

Figure 27-4: Tinkercad Simulation

Figure 28-4: Circuit Diagram

Table 9-4: Test Cases

Test Case	Description	Expected Output	Result
Flex Sensor Reading	Check if the Arduino correctly reads the flex sensor values.	Serial Monitor displays varying sensor values.	✓
Gesture Recognition	Verify that specific flex sensor values match predefined gestures.	Correct gesture is identified and mapped.	✓
System Stability	Check for consistent operation over an extended period.	System continues to function without crashes.	✓

Acceptance Criteria:

- The system should accurately read flex sensor values and distinguish different gestures.
- The Android device should display the correct text corresponding to each recognized gesture.
- The system should function without noticeable delays or errors in gesture recognition.

4.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, we covered the implementation, simulation, and testing of the glove-based translation system. The glove was successfully developed using Arduino, flex sensors, and the HC-05, allowing for accurate gesture recognition and real-time transmission to an Android device.

The project was simulated using Tinkercad, ensuring that the hardware and software components functioned as expected before physical development. Through various test cases, we validated sensor responsiveness and gesture recognition accuracy. The system met all the predefined acceptance criteria, demonstrating its effectiveness in facilitating communication for individuals with hearing or speech impairments.

Overall, the implementation and testing confirm that the proposed system is a practical, cost-effective, and accessible solution for translating gestures into text, making communication more inclusive.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Conclusion

In this project, we successfully developed a Gesture-to-Text translation system using Arduino and an Android application. The system captures finger bending using flex sensors and transmits the recognized gestures wirelessly over Bluetooth to an Android device. The Android app receives the data and displays the corresponding text in real time.

This work demonstrates how low-cost sensors and wireless modules can be combined to create an effective assistive tool for people with speech or hearing impairments. Key lessons learned include the difference between low-cost and high-cost sensors, the importance of accurate sensor calibration, the challenges of wireless data transmission stability (especially with non-ASCII characters like Arabic), and user interface design considerations for clear and readable text output.

5.2 Future Work

Several opportunities exist to improve this project into a widely usable system, such as:

- **Multi-Language Support:** Enhance the system to support more languages beyond Arabic and English.
- **Gesture Database Expansion:** Add recognition for more complex gestures, including dynamic (motion-based) signs, using machine learning algorithms.
- **Speech Output:** Integrate text-to-speech functionality in the Android app to provide voice output, making communication even smoother.

APPENDIX A: IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

1. Sensor Calibration

Each flex sensor was calibrated individually to account for variations in sensor resistance. The raw analog values from the Arduino (0–1023) were tested while the fingers were in straight and bent positions to reduce false positives while ensuring sensitivity.

2. Bluetooth Communication

The HC-05 module was configured at a 9600 baud rate, using standard serial communication.

3. Layout Design (Tablet Optimized)

The Android UI was designed using [ConstraintLayout] to adapt to a 10.5-inch tablet in landscape mode.

4. Power Supply Considerations

The glove and Arduino system can be powered by a power bank for portability. Voltage levels were checked to ensure compatibility with the HC-05 module, which operates at 5V.

APPENDIX B: USER MANUAL

This manual describes how to use the Gesture-to-Text Translation App with the glove device.

1. Requirements

- Android Device (10.5-inch tablet recommended, Android 5.0 or later)
- Bluetooth module (HC-05)
- Arduino with glove and flex sensors
- Power source (laptop or power bank) for the Arduino system

2. Setup Steps

1. Turn On the Glove System

- a. Power on the Arduino glove system with a power source.
- b. Ensure the HC-05 module starts blinking (indicating pairing mode).

2. Pair Bluetooth Module

- a. On the tablet, go to Settings → Bluetooth.
- b. Find HC-05 in the list of devices.
- c. Tap to pair. The default PIN is usually (1234 or 0000).

3. Open the App

- a. Launch the Gesture-to-Text Translation app from the home screen.

4. Connect Bluetooth

- a.** Tap the Connect button at the bottom.
- b.** Wait for the "Connected" message.

5. Use the Glove

- a.** Perform gestures with your right-hand glove.
- b.** The detected word or phrase will appear in large text in the center of the screen.

3. Notes

- Keep the glove within 5-10 meters of the tablet for best Bluetooth performance.
- Avoid obstacles like walls between the glove and tablet.

APPENDIX C: DEPLOYMENT AND CONFIGURATION MANUAL

This section outlines how to deploy and configure the system.

1. Hardware Deployment

- **Arduino + Glove:**
 - Connect the glove to the breadboard.
 - Attach the HC-05 Bluetooth module:
 - TX to Arduino pin 7
 - RX to Arduino pin 8
 - Power the system via a power source.

2. Android App Deployment:

- Install the app APK on your device.
- Ensure Bluetooth and Location permissions are granted.

3. Configuration Details

- **Bluetooth Module (HC-05):**
 - Pairing PIN: usually 1234 or 0000
- **Flex Sensors:**
 - Monitor the change in sensor value when fully bent and unbent using Arduino IDE.
 - Calculate the average value of each sensor and place it as the threshold value for each finger.

4. Troubleshooting:

Table 10-C: Troubleshooting

Problem	Solution
The app shows "Connection failed"	Ensure HC-05 is powered and paired
Gesture output mismatch	Recalibrate the sensor threshold values
Text flickers or glitches	Check Arduino is sending a proper newline
Tablet not receiving or displaying gestures	Ensure the app has Bluetooth permissions enabled.
Range issues	Keep the glove within 5-10 meters of the tablet
No sensor readings	Ensure the flex sensor provides significant resistance variation (typically from $\sim 10\text{k}\Omega$ to $\sim 30\text{k}\Omega$).

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